
Addressing the Challenges Posed by Anaconda's New Licensing Model

A White Paper for Researchers, Research Computing Facilitators, and Institutional Leadership

CaRCC Anaconda Transition Working Group

Contents

1	Executive Summary	2
2	Introduction	2
3	Impact on Academic Institutions	5
4	Licensing and Cost Implications	6
5	Compliance Concerns	7
6	Alternative Solutions and Recommendations	9
7	Conclusion	11
8	Appendix	11

Authors

Anna Alber,¹ Joseph Creech,² Raffaella D'Auria,³ Lev Gorenstein,⁴ Manasvita Joshi,⁵ Ian Kaufman,⁶ Geoffrey Lentner,⁷ Bryan Raney,⁸ Aldo Romero,⁹ William Warriner¹⁰

¹ Chapman University; ² George Washington University; ³ OARC/IDRE - University of California, Los Angeles; ⁴ Globus - University of Chicago; ⁵ Harvard University; ⁶ University of California, San Diego; ⁷ Purdue University; ⁸ Rice University; ⁹ West Virginia University; ¹⁰ University of Alabama at Birmingham.

Version

1.0.0

Date

2026-06-14

1 Executive Summary

When Anaconda Inc. introduced its revised Terms of Service (ToS) in March 2024, the changes created immediate uncertainty for academic research computing. For years, Anaconda’s Python distribution and package-management platform had been freely available for academic use across both local systems and HPC clusters, serving as the foundation for scientific workflows in many departments. Institutions that rely on shared local systems and HPC clusters faced concerns about compliance scope, budget exposure, and potential disruption to established collaborative workflows. This work reflects that context while focusing on practical and current paths forward.

1.1 For the Community

The conda package manager is free and open-source. It is not going away. The licensing concerns are specifically about packages hosted in Anaconda Inc.’s “defaults” channel and their distribution platform. **For most users, the simplest path forward is to use conda-forge¹ as your package channel** (e.g., by installing Miniforge² instead of the Anaconda distribution). Conda-forge is a large, community-maintained collection of packages that does not fall under Anaconda’s Terms of Service. You can continue using conda (or mamba) exactly as before, just sourcing packages from conda-forge instead of “defaults.”

That said, Anaconda Inc. does provide value beyond just hosting packages. Their curated “defaults” channel undergoes additional vetting, which may matter for institutions with stringent security or reproducibility requirements. Organizations in regulated or high-security environments may find Anaconda’s commercial offerings, including verified package provenance and enterprise support, worth evaluating. For others, conda-forge covers most scientific computing needs at no cost and with no licensing concerns.

1.2 For Institutional Leadership

Anaconda Inc.’s revised [Terms of Service](#)³, effective July 15, 2025, introduce new compliance obligations for academic institutions. While Anaconda remains free for accredited educational entities under their [Academic Policy](#)⁴, institutions must now proactively secure an Eligible Academic Institution (EAI) agreement, renewed annually, and are held responsible for ensuring all users comply with the terms. Key risk areas include restrictions on embedding Anaconda packages in containers, mirroring repositories, and providing access to third parties (e.g., external collaborators), all of which may require a paid license even under the academic exemption. The terms can be modified with ninety days’ notice, posted to Anaconda’s legal page, and it falls to the institution to monitor for those changes. Given this evolving landscape, the working group recommends that institutions evaluate open-source alternatives (such as Miniforge with conda-forge) to reduce compliance exposure, while engaging with peer institutions through [CaRCC](#)⁵ to advocate for clearer, more stable academic terms.

2 Introduction

Anaconda has long been a cornerstone of scientific and academic computing, offering a robust package management system and an ecosystem that simplifies the installation and maintenance of numerous open-source libraries. It is one of the most popular methods of automatically installing packages and interfacing

¹ <https://conda-forge.org/>

² <https://conda-forge.org/download/>

³ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/terms-of-service>

⁴ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/academic>

⁵ <https://carcc.org/anaconda-transition-working-group/>

with AI and other package-based technologies. However, in March 2024, Anaconda Inc. updated its ToS⁶ to imply that it would no longer support free access to their base distribution or their “defaults” channel for organizations with more than 200 employees, raising concerns that large academic and research institutions could be affected. The reason⁷ for updating their ToS was to offset the significant costs associated with maintaining and hosting their platform and services. But this update created significant uncertainty across academic communities that have historically relied upon Anaconda for their academic and research work, particularly regarding compliance scope and budget exposure.

In September 2024, a few months after the aforementioned changes to the ToS, a blog post⁸ was published to clarify the intent of the update to the community. This blog post seemed to suggest that Anaconda would remain free for researchers at accredited universities though universities cannot mirror Anaconda servers without a license, and that a revised update was forthcoming by the year-end. The Community Repository on anaconda.org⁹ is free to use for installing and updating packages from community channels like conda-forge, but certain mirrored channels (main, r, msys2, anaconda) remain subject to [Anaconda’s Terms of Service](#)¹⁰. The Anaconda Repository at repo.anaconda.com¹¹ is also free for individuals, universities, and companies with fewer than 200 employees, but larger non-academic organizations, including research institutions and national labs, must obtain a license to use it. However, the academic community continued to stay concerned, as blog posts are not legally binding (unlike ToS, which were eventually updated in July 2025), which led to the creation of [Anaconda Transition Working Group](#)¹² (ATWG).

ATWG comes under the umbrella of the nationwide Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC¹³). It was formed to help the research computing and data (RCD) community ensure compliance with the changes proposed by Anaconda Inc., evaluate potential complications arising from the update, and to come up with alternatives for package management that could be used as possible workarounds. Since its inception in October 2024, ATWG has been meeting weekly to discuss the implications of Anaconda Inc.’s revised ToS and how to best communicate that to the academic community. To that end, the group has met with the Anaconda Inc. a few times, in December 2024, February 2025, and July 2025, to gain clarity on their ToS, ensure compliance in the face of the changes proposed by Anaconda Inc., and obtain updates on the ToS as pertaining to the academic community. The goals of the meetings included, but were not limited to:

- obtaining clarity on the [update to the ToS](#)¹⁴
- the current status of proposed changes
- implications of the change on the larger community
- thoughts and suggestions on how to proceed
- specific compliance details for various types of institutions

Before proceeding further, it is important to make the distinction between several terms used here. Anaconda, as a term, could refer to the company, a package distribution channel, or a package management software distribution, depending on the context. It could, sometimes, also be used to refer to the environ-

⁶ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/terms-of-service>

⁷ <https://web.archive.org/web/20240905131946/https://www.anaconda.com/pricing/terms-of-service-faqs>

⁸ <https://www.anaconda.com/blog/update-on-anacondas-terms-of-service-for-academia-and-research>

⁹ <https://anaconda.org>

¹⁰ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/terms-of-service>

¹¹ <https://repo.anaconda.com/>

¹² <https://carcc.org/anaconda-transition-working-group/>

¹³ <https://carcc.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/terms-of-service>

ment management software “conda”. On the other hand, [Anaconda, Inc.](https://www.anaconda.com/)¹⁵, strictly refers to the privately owned, for-profit company responsible for the well-known ecosystem for managing scientific software packages. Finally, Anaconda distribution refers to the software bundle containing “conda”, Anaconda Navigator (desktop application with graphical interface for managing packages, channels, and environments within the Anaconda, Inc. ecosystem), a pre-configured “base” environment, and pre-configured package distribution channels.

According to the updated ToS, downloading the distribution is covered by the ToS. However, the Anaconda channel that is maintained by the company is subject to the licensing restrictions described in the ToS. Additionally, “conda” and its [repository](https://github.com/conda/conda)¹⁶ is Free and Open-Source Software (FOSS) under the 3-clause Berkeley Software Distribution ([BSD-3-Clause](https://opensource.org/licenses/BSD-3-Clause)¹⁷) license that is widely used in the Anaconda Distribution, Miniconda, and Miniforge installers. At the time, the primary issues associated with the changes in the ToS included, but were not limited to:

- **Licensing Costs:** It appeared that institutions with more than 200 employees would need to pay for a commercial license to use Anaconda.
- **Compliance:** Some institutions reported receiving notices from Anaconda asserting non-compliance with the new ToS, in some cases with warnings of back-billing for prior usage (as reported by [The Register](https://www.theregister.com/2024/08/08/anaconda_puts_the_squeeze_on/)¹⁸).
- **Heavy Dependence:** Academic institutions contribute significantly to open-source software used within Anaconda. Based on the above, it was feared that any institution with more than 200 employees, including universities, would be required to pay for access.
- **Budget Constraints:** Many institutions and researchers operate under tight budgets, even more so now than ever, that do not account for unexpected licensing costs.
- **Operational Challenges:** The implementation of these changes has disrupted workflows, requiring rapid reassessment of how institutions and research computing teams should manage software environments.

To address these challenges, ATWG had initiated several actions:

- **Communication with Anaconda Inc.:** As noted above, we had three meetings with Anaconda Inc. leadership and representatives, in addition to a few exchanges over email. The main goals of those meetings were to understand their licensing model better and to advocate for equitable treatment of academic institutions.
- **Internal collaboration:** Institutions within CaRCC shared their experiences and strategies for adapting to the new licensing model, including alternative solutions. ATWG had reached out to CaRCC community members in the form of a user survey to understand their usage and the level of dependence on Anaconda.
- **Exploring alternatives:** Discussions were carried out to evaluate alternative tools and approaches for managing software environments. This included exploring open-source installers, such as Miniforge,

¹⁵ <https://www.anaconda.com/>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/conda/conda>

¹⁷ <https://opensource.org/licenses/bsd-3-clause>

¹⁸ https://www.theregister.com/2024/08/08/anaconda_puts_the_squeeze_on/

and utilizing package managers like [Mamba](#)¹⁹, [Pip](#)²⁰, [Pixi](#)²¹, and/or [uv](#)²². Additionally, containerization platforms like [Singularity/Apptainer](#)²³ or [Docker](#)²⁴ as possible alternatives to package management, as long as they employed open-source installers, and installing packages from scratch were explored.

3 Impact on Academic Institutions

At the time of Anaconda’s updates-to-ToS announcement, academic organizations faced a range of practical and financial challenges:

1. Escalating Licensing Costs

Based on the original announcement, it was perceived that any institution with more than 200 employees must purchase a commercial license. For a typical mid-sized university—supporting dozens of departments, central IT-managed HPC clusters, and distributed lab installations—annual fees could reach tens of thousands of dollars. These unplanned expenses threaten to divert funding away from core research and teaching needs.

2. Compliance Ambiguity

CaRCC members reported receiving “non-compliance” notices for shared installations on central clusters. This raised a number of key questions that remained unanswered; these are discussed in the [Compliance Concerns](#) section.

3. Transition Overhead

Moving away from Anaconda—whether to [conda-forge/Miniforge](#), [Spack](#), or containers—requires substantial IT staff time, retraining of faculty and students, and revalidation of research pipelines. One peer university estimated that piloting a [Spack](#) migration consumed over 200 staff-hours and delayed several high-priority simulation campaigns by weeks.

4. Disruption to Scientific Workflows

Researchers rely on the ease of [conda](#) install and prebuilt binary packages for everything from molecular dynamics to machine-learning toolkits. Any interruption in Anaconda service risks halting active data analyses, reproducibility efforts, and deadline-driven computational experiments.

5. Complications for Collaboration

In multi-institution projects — such as DOE lab partnerships or interdisciplinary centers — a fragmented licensing landscape could force collaborators onto different package ecosystems, undermining shared environment files, container images, and joint development workflows.

6. Strained Budgets and Sustainability

Redirecting grant funds and departmental budgets toward license fees may force difficult trade-offs: hiring fewer graduate students, postponing hardware upgrades, or reducing support for other open-source tools critical to our teaching and research missions.

¹⁹ <https://mamba.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²⁰ https://packaging.python.org/en/latest/key_projects/#pip

²¹ <https://pixi.prefix.dev/latest/>

²² <https://docs.astral.sh/uv/>

²³ <https://apptainer.org/docs/user/latest/>

²⁴ <https://www.docker.com/>

4 Licensing and Cost Implications

At the start of 2025, Anaconda Inc. released²⁵ [Anaconda for Education](#)²⁶ to accelerate AI learning across the academic community for free of charge. This includes access to free AI courses, storage, and tools at no cost to users, such as researchers, students, and educators with an academic access to the Anaconda Starter plan. The products and tools that are included in this package are [Anaconda Distribution](#)²⁷, [Anaconda Navigator](#)²⁸, [Anaconda AI Assistant](#)²⁹, [Public Package Repository](#)³⁰, [Anaconda Learning](#)³¹, [Cloud Notebooks](#)³², and [App publishing with Panel](#)³³.

In July 2025, Anaconda Inc. published their revised ToS³⁴, according to which Anaconda does not require academic institutions and universities to purchase a commercial fee license for their installers or for access to their [package repository](#)³⁵, regardless of their size, when used in course curricula, including teaching, learning, and research at accredited educational institutions worldwide. Accredited academic institutions qualify for free use regardless of size; the 200-employee threshold for paid licenses applies to for-profit (commercial) organizations, not to universities. However, it is important to note that paid licenses may be required for specific use cases within academic settings, such as embedding Anaconda’s products, mirroring them, or providing third-party access beyond standard educational use.

In order to access the academic account one needs to be either actively enrolled or employed at an accredited academic institution with a verified academic email address. As mentioned above, for an accredited academic institution, the use of Anaconda package repository continues to be free and they do not need to purchase any business or enterprise license regardless of their size. The free-use policy for educational entities continues to be in effect as long as Anaconda is used in the institution’s course curricula, teaching, learning, and research. In addition to academia, Anaconda Inc. now offers AI-based solutions by industry that include finance, healthcare, government, manufacturing, and technology. All of the categories come with their own price packages except for academia, where the use is free as long as no embedding, mirroring, or access to a third party has been carried out for their products. However, they urge institutions to contact their [partner team](#)³⁶ at partnerships@anaconda.com should the need to pursue an embedded use case arise in academia. Anaconda’s archival FAQ from [September 5, 2024](#)³⁷ already declared: “A paid license is always required for any individual or entity that is embedding, mirroring, or providing third parties access to [its] products,” without carving out an exception for academic use. The more recent materials are notable instead for adding an explicit academic exemption and directing institutions to the partner team for embedded academic use cases.

Given that the state of affairs is still evolving at Anaconda Inc. and that there is a fair amount of ambiguity in what would constitute as an out-of-compliance case and when would a license be required, the ATWG has decided to come up with a number of recommendations for the academic community that rely upon alternative methods to achieve what can be accomplished with Anaconda distribution. Additionally, while

²⁵ <https://www.anaconda.com/blog/anaconda-for-education-empowering-the-academic-community>

²⁶ <https://www.anaconda.com/industries/education>

²⁷ <https://www.anaconda.com/download>

²⁸ <https://www.anaconda.com/products/ai-navigator>

²⁹ <https://www.anaconda.com/capability/anaconda-assistant>

³⁰ <https://repo.anaconda.com/>

³¹ <https://www.anaconda.com/learning>

³² <https://www.anaconda.com/products/notebooks>

³³ <https://www.anaconda.com/blog/a-new-and-simple-way-to-publish-your-data-applications>

³⁴ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/terms-of-service>

³⁵ <https://repo.anaconda.com/>

³⁶ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal>

³⁷ <https://web.archive.org/web/20240905131946/https://www.anaconda.com/pricing/terms-of-service-faqs>

Anaconda Inc.'s Terms of Service hold the accepting institution responsible for ensuring its users comply with those Terms and for any violations by those users, ATWG holds that, as a practical matter, campus research computing teams are not well positioned to continuously monitor or enforce individual end-user behavior in how Anaconda Inc. products are used on shared academic and research clusters. Hence, having alternative solutions would help the research community decide, in an informed manner, on how to proceed with package management.

The proposed solutions are all based on open-source software and distribution that do not depend on any of the Anaconda Inc. products, thereby allowing us to avoid any license or out-of-compliance issues with them. A summarized version of these solutions is mentioned in the *Alternative Solutions and Recommendations* section, whereas a detailed description of utilizing these methods is provided in the *Appendix*.

5 Compliance Concerns

The recent changes to Anaconda's licensing model, which limit the previously free distribution and usage of its platform for non-commercial purposes, have raised significant compliance concerns for academic and research institutions. These concerns are especially critical as institutions balance the need for cutting-edge research tools with the strict legal and regulatory frameworks governing their operations. As such, educational entities are exempt from the paid license requirement provided they use Anaconda Offering(s) solely for curriculum-based course or non-commercial research where the Anaconda Offering(s) is guaranteed to be not mirrored, embedded, or redistributed.

1. Licensing Restrictions and Compliance Risks:

Anaconda's previous licensing model allowed academic and research institutions to use the distribution platform freely without incurring licensing fees, provided the use was non-commercial in nature. This model has allowed institutions to develop and deploy software environments, often across large-scale high-performance computing (HPC) systems, with minimal administrative burden.

However, the new licensing changes, particularly for non-commercial users, could potentially introduce the risk of non-compliance in the following areas:

License/Agreement Enforcement:

Institutions must now ensure that any use of Anaconda's distribution within non-commercial research environments adheres to the new terms.

According to their current *Academic Policy*³⁸, an institution qualifying for an Eligible Academic Institution (EAI) account should secure an institution-wide agreement for use of Anaconda. The institution must reach out to their support team to initiate the process of completing the EAI Agreement with Anaconda and set up an academic account. However, the agreement prohibits researchers/users from extending their scaled enterprise deployment to commercial, non-educational use while using Anaconda at an EAI. This also includes redistribution of system outputs, which is permitted only within the scope of non-commercial, educational use under the Academic Policy.

Anaconda reserves the right to verify the institution's eligibility for the Anaconda for Education Program, and access to this program's benefits is valid for twelve months from the signing of the EAI Agreement (or, for an individual participant, from signing the Academic End User License Agreement). Once that period expires, the agreement must be renewed to continue accessing the benefits; renewal requires Anaconda to

³⁸ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/academic>

re-verify eligibility and the participants to re-sign their agreements. The institution must also report any material change that may affect its eligibility to Anaconda within thirty (30) days of such change.

Additionally, Anaconda extends participation in this program to individuals associated with an EAI, provided each participating individual signs the Anaconda Academic End User License Agreement. However, according to their current [Terms of Service](#)³⁹, section 5, the institution would be responsible for ensuring that all their users follow these Terms and for any violations of these Terms by their users. In the case of any modification to the terms of their Academic Policy, Anaconda will post them to [Anaconda's legal page](#)⁴⁰ with a ninety day notice. The program participants will not be directly notified but it will be their responsibility to review the terms of this Policy periodically to ensure that no new updates have been released.

All of the above puts an additional responsibility on the institution's representative to ensure that the institution-wide agreement remains valid, is adhered to at all times, and policy changes are tracked regularly to avoid any legal complications that might originate from lack of thereof.

Auditability:

Without clear mechanisms in place to track which users are operating under the free or paid licenses, research institutions risk running afoul of audit processes. Many institutions are subject to external audits, particularly when dealing with government-funded research or grants, and failing to demonstrate compliance with software licensing requirements can result in penalties or reputational damage. Anaconda's Terms of Service reinforce this exposure: customers must retain usage records for the duration of the subscription term and for twelve months after it ends, must provide them on request to confirm compliance, and may be charged for any excess users at Anaconda's then-current pricing.

2. Potential Legal Implications:

Academic institutions are often bound by stringent intellectual property agreements, especially those that receive government or private funding. The violation of software licensing agreements may have downstream legal consequences, including:

Loss of Funding:

Non-compliance with software licenses could lead to the forfeiture of funding, particularly when grantors specify that software tools and infrastructure must be licensed properly and legally.

Legal Disputes:

Institutions that inadvertently breach Anaconda's new licensing terms could face contractual demands and, in principle, litigation. While legal action might be rare, even the risk of potential lawsuits can cause significant disruptions and reputational harm to an institution, which is particularly concerning for publicly-funded research.

3. Institutional Governance and Policy Updates:

Institutions must review and potentially update their governance and policy frameworks to reflect these new licensing terms. Specific areas for policy development and review may include:

IT Policies:

Updating institutional IT policies to ensure that all research computing resources, including HPC clusters, are compliant with Anaconda's new licensing terms. This includes developing clear guidelines for faculty and researchers regarding which licenses are required for specific projects or environments.

³⁹ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/terms-of-service>

⁴⁰ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms>

Procurement Processes:

Revising procurement processes to account for the financial and legal implications of new licensing models. This could involve negotiating blanket licenses for entire departments or campuses or deciding whether to migrate to alternative software solutions to mitigate compliance risk.

4. Secure Environment Cluster:

Institutions operating a secure environment cluster would need to evaluate the security level of their cluster to decide whether the purchase of Anaconda's distribution is warranted. For example, a cluster that must meet federally recognized security standards such as NIST 800-53 or NIST 800-171 is subject to supply-chain and system-integrity requirements — for instance, maintaining a supply-chain risk management plan, documenting and verifying component provenance, and identifying and remediating known vulnerabilities. These standards specify functional and process outcomes rather than mandating any particular vendor or product, and can be met with a controlled internal mirror, transparently built channels such as conda-forge, and SBOM and vulnerability scanning combined with documented review processes. Meeting them with purely open-source tooling does, however, place the burden of provenance documentation, vulnerability triage, and support on the institution. For such regulated or high-security deployments, institutions should evaluate whether a commercial offering with built-in provenance, auditing, and vendor support — such as Anaconda Inc.'s [Anaconda Business](#)⁴¹, an enterprise-grade package repository — better fits their compliance and operational needs. Most clusters housing sensitive datasets under a Data Usage Agreement (DUA) and/or IRB approval can still use the alternative methods mentioned below for installing packages.

Keeping all of the above in mind, some of the key questions that still remain unanswered are:

- Does the academic free-use program cover external collaborators who lack an appointment and academic email at an Eligible Academic Institution, given that individual participation requires signing the Academic End User License Agreement and registering with an academic email address? Researchers affiliated with a qualifying non-profit or research organization may instead be eligible under Anaconda Inc.'s Non-Profit & Research Policy, which nonetheless excludes government-affiliated institutions, Federally Funded Research and Development Centers (FFRDCs), and the U.S. Department of Energy National Laboratories.
- Would it be possible for the research community to obtain further clarity from Anaconda Inc. on free distribution of containerization platforms, such as Singularity/Apptainer or Docker?

Hence, exploring alternative open-source solutions for managing packages and installing software for scientific workflows is imperative for the research community to proceed with their research and collaboration in an informed manner.

6 Alternative Solutions and Recommendations

Given the compliance challenges raised by Anaconda's new licensing model, academic and research institutions need to explore alternative solutions to mitigate both financial and operational risks. Below are several viable options that can help institutions maintain operational efficiency and compliance while reducing dependency on Anaconda's paid licensing structure.

1. Open-Source Package Management Systems

⁴¹ <https://www.anaconda.com/guides/the-ultimate-guide-to-open-source-security-with-python-and-r#:~:text=Anaconda%20Business%20is%20an%20enterprise%2Dgrade%20package%20repository,do%20not%20comply%20with%20your%20legal%20requirements.>

One of the most straightforward alternatives is to transition to fully open-source package management systems that can replace Anaconda’s distribution platform, offering similar functionality without licensing restrictions, such as conda-forge. This allows institutions to create isolated environments without requiring a paid license. For a full list of options, see *Appendix*.

2. Docker and Containerization

Containerization platforms provide another viable alternative by allowing research institutions to build and deploy reproducible research environments in isolated containers. Containerization allows users to create self-contained, portable images that can be deployed across other computing platforms more easily. These containers can also be prebuilt to include alternative open-source environments and the necessary software packages, eliminating the need for the Anaconda distribution.

Anaconda Inc.’s *Terms of Service*⁴² (effective July 15, 2025; accessed August 29, 2025) prevent “embedding” (“incorporating Anaconda Content into another product or service as a built-in component or continually updating dependency of a larger software application”) and prevent “distribut[ing] the Platform or any Offering to anyone other than your Users.” The same definition adds a carve-out: “Embedding does not include providing services or processing data for third parties, as long as the third party does not interact with the Anaconda Offering.” Anaconda Inc.’s *Academic Policy*⁴³ (effective July 14, 2025; accessed August 29, 2025) creates a limited exemption from these restrictions, allowing one “to redistribute system outputs solely for academic purposes,” though the term “system outputs” is not defined in either the Terms of Service or the Academic Policy.

Our concern with these restrictions is a common use-case of a researcher creating a Docker (or Singularity/Apptainer) Container to share their code and/or workflows with other researchers, possibly at other academic institutions. If that researcher includes Anaconda Inc. packages within the container image, it could be considered “embedding,” which is not allowed; the embedding carve-out does not appear to help here, since a researcher who receives the container interacts with the bundled Anaconda Content directly. Sharing that container with others outside their own Institution would appear to count as “distribution”. Whether a Container image qualifies as “system outputs” — and is therefore covered by the Academic Policy’s distribution exemption — is unclear, so sharing one might not be allowed outside the originating Institution. On the other hand, that exemption permits redistribution only insofar as it “remains within the scope of non-commercial, educational use,” which researcher-to-researcher academic sharing would plausibly satisfy; the unresolved question is whether a container image counts as a “system output” at all.

The only solution we see in this case is to make sure that the restricted Anaconda Inc. packages are not included in any Containers. However, it would be quite difficult for any Institution to monitor the behavior of all researchers at the level of creating and/or sharing Container images. A given image could be potentially scanned for Anaconda, Inc.’s packages, but it is not always clear where a Container image has come from, or with whom it might have been shared.

3. Virtual Machines (VMs) and Cloud-based Solutions

For institutions that require greater flexibility and scalability, moving to cloud-based research environments or using virtual machines (VMs) can provide another way to sidestep licensing issues while ensuring compliance. Institutions can also create custom virtual machines with specific research environments, using open-source package managers, to replace Anaconda environments. These VMs can be hosted on local servers or on cloud platforms.

⁴² <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/terms-of-service>

⁴³ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/academic>

4. Hybrid Solutions: Combining Multiple Tools

In many cases, institutions may find it effective to combine multiple alternative solutions based on specific needs.

Each of these alternative solutions offers different trade-offs in terms of cost, compliance, and operational complexity. The best solution for any given institution will depend on its specific needs, infrastructure, and available resources.

If an institution decides to move away from Anaconda's licensing model, they should evaluate the potential of these solutions based on their current research tools, budget constraints, and long-term goals. A hybrid approach that incorporates multiple tools may provide the greatest flexibility and minimize both the compliance risks and operational burdens of the new licensing restrictions.

7 Conclusion

While Anaconda's licensing changes pose significant challenges, they also present an opportunity to reexamine our dependencies and develop more resilient software ecosystems. Through collaboration and proactive planning, we can ensure that academic research continues to thrive without disruption. To that end, our recommendations to the community are mentioned below.

7.1 Recommendations:

We propose the following actions to mitigate the impact:

1. **Continue Advocacy:** Strengthen dialogue with Anaconda to seek adjustments that better support academic institutions, such as discounted or waived fees for specific use cases.
2. **Leverage Community Collaboration:** Build on the efforts within CaRCC to document and share best practices for managing the transition.
3. **Evaluate and Pilot Alternatives:** Proactively explore and test alternative package management and distribution solutions to reduce reliance on Anaconda. See *Appendix*
4. **Establish Contingency Plans:** Develop strategies to ensure research continuity if access to Anaconda becomes restricted or unsustainable.

8 Appendix

8.1 Scripts and Tools

The Anaconda Transition Working Group set up a directory of scripts and tools to assist institutions with their migration from Anaconda commercial channels. These are available in the `Misc/tools` directory of the project repository: <https://github.com/CaRCC/anaconda-transition/tree/main/Misc/tools>

8.2 Open-source Solutions

Below is a list of open-source options that the ATWG has put together. This is not a complete list but is a good starting point should an institution or a research team decide to go the open-source route. Some of the solutions do not represent a full alternative to Anaconda.

- Conda (the BSD-3-Clause package manager behind Anaconda; fully open-source). Miniconda (a minimal Anaconda installer that defaults to Anaconda’s repository, so reconfigure it to conda-forge or another community channel to stay outside the Terms of Service)
- Miniforge (pulls from conda-forge by default; Mambaforge was deprecated in July 2024)
- Mamba (drop-in replacement for Conda written in C++, bundled with Miniforge since version 23.3.1)
- Pixi (Rust-based package, environment, and project manager with seamless mixing of PyPI + Conda packages, conda-forge by default)
- uv (Rust-based, ultra-fast Python package, environment and project manager)
- Pip (pulls from PyPI)
- Pip + venv/virtualenv
- pipx (Not a full environment manager, installs Python CLI tools in isolated environments)
- Poetry (project dependency and packaging manager)
- Pipenv (Uses Pipfile + Pipfile.lock for reproducible environments)

8.3 Conda vs Mamba

Conda⁴⁴ and Mamba⁴⁵ are package managers and command-line tools, they can be used mostly interchangeably as Mamba was created as a drop-in replacement for Conda (with a largely compatible CLI, with minor differences). Both support channels like `conda-forge`⁴⁶ and Anaconda’s defaults⁴⁷. The use of Anaconda Inc.’s “defaults” channels is subjected to Anaconda Inc.’s ToS⁴⁸.

Conda is written in python and Mamba is written C/C++ and has a faster dependency resolution as it uses `libsolv`⁴⁹, which is a fast dependency solver also used by Linux package managers, and it can also parallelize downloads speeding installation further. As of version 23.10.0⁵⁰ conda uses by default the `conda-libmamba-solver` plugin which allows conda to use the same `libsolv` solver used by mamba (see: <https://conda.github.io/conda-libmamba-solver/user-guide/>).

Conda can be used independently of the Anaconda distribution (which uses conda as its package manager but also includes tools such as `Spyder`⁵¹). Mamba was originally developed by `QuantStack`⁵² and is distributed by QuantStack and Mamba contributors. Both package managers are open source and licensed under the BSD 3-Clause License.

Conda and Mamba are general purpose package managers which offer support for: python, R, C/C++, JavaScript/node, compilers, etc. Alternatives to conda and mamba are generally only available for python (and for specific versions of python) and do not cover system libraries.

⁴⁴ <https://github.com/conda/conda>

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/mamba-org/mamba>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/conda-forge>

⁴⁷ <https://www.anaconda.com/docs/getting-started/working-with-conda/reference/default-channels>

⁴⁸ <https://www.anaconda.com/legal/terms/terms-of-service>

⁴⁹ <https://github.com/openSUSE/libsolv>

⁵⁰ <https://conda.github.io/conda-libmamba-solver/user-guide/>

⁵¹ <https://www.spyder-ide.org/>

⁵² <https://quantstack.net/>

There are numerous permutations of these tools for installers available that include different combinations of the components described here. These include “micromamba” (a standalone static binary that needs no base environment) and the now-deprecated “mambaforge”.

8.4 Conda vs Miniforge and alternate conda package channels

You can continue to use conda as a package manager, but would need to configure it to only install packages from community-provided sources that do not require a license. Conda packages are organized into channels⁵³, where each channel is a different source for packaged software.

Conda typically comes configured to install packages from the “defaults” channel, which supplies packages from the Anaconda, Inc. repository. Use of those packages may require a license from Anaconda, Inc. A common alternative channel is [conda-forge](https://conda-forge.org/)⁵⁴, which provides a large collection of community-supplied packages. Another commonly used community channel is [bioconda](https://bioconda.github.io/)⁵⁵.

According to Anaconda Inc.’s archival FAQ from [May 2025](https://www.anaconda.com/faq/)⁵⁶, it may not be necessary to block Anaconda.com channels outright. Nevertheless, ATWG conducted its own tests by blocking the [Anaconda repository](https://www.anaconda.com/faq/)⁵⁷ and confirmed that packages can still be installed using the bioconda channel, or Python packages in R using the [reticulate package](https://www.rstudio.com/products/reticulate/)⁵⁸ with packages installed from the conda-forge channel, without any issues. See the [Block Anaconda Repo](#) section for details on these tests.

8.5 Important Update on the “defaults” Channel

- Conda-forge has released a transition guide for migrating away from the “defaults” channel in the context of miniforge. Note that the “defaults” channel has been deprecated and scheduled for removal in version 25.9.

Resources

- Transition Guide: https://conda-forge.org/docs/user/transitioning_from_defaults/
- Deprecation Postponement Details: <https://github.com/conda/conda/pull/14662>

8.6 Additional recommendations if using conda-forge

- Using conda-forge, if you don’t already have conda installed

Install “Miniforge” instead of installing the Anaconda distribution or Miniconda. Miniforge is a version of conda that is pre-configured to only access the “conda-forge” channel. See <https://conda-forge.org/download/> for this option. The downside of Miniforge is that unlike the standard Anaconda distribution, Miniforge does not create a rich “base” environment with 300+ packages to get you started. Rather, Miniforge’s “base” environment is intentionally minimalistic and is meant to serve the functionality of the installer itself. You will then need to either populate this “base” environment with packages of your choice, or to create additional conda environment(s) and specify which packages you want to use. The command would look something like:

⁵³ <https://docs.conda.io/projects/conda/en/latest/user-guide/concepts/channels.html>

⁵⁴ <https://conda-forge.org/>

⁵⁵ <https://bioconda.github.io/>

⁵⁶ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250506034856/https://www.anaconda.com/pricing/terms-of-service-faq>

⁵⁷ <https://repo.anaconda.com>

⁵⁸ <https://rstudio.github.io/reticulate/>

```
$ conda create -n environment_name package1 package2 ... packageN
```

For a more specific example:

```
$ conda create -n mypandas numpy pandas
```

- Using conda-forge, if you already have conda installed

You can see which channels conda is configured to use like so:

```
$ conda config --show channels
channels:
- defaults
```

You can then swap one channel for the other like so:

```
$ conda config --prepend channels conda-forge
$ conda config --remove channels defaults
$ conda config --show channels
channels:
- conda-forge
```

“Conda-forge” is a large community, but may not have every package you need. If you are interested in a particular package, you can find if any channels offer it by searching for it on the anaconda.org website (not the same as anaconda.com). If you find a channel you want conda to install packages from, you can add it to the conda configuration as was done in the above example.

Note

While the community-provided packages are stored on Anaconda, Inc.’s servers as a courtesy, they are not owned or created by Anaconda, Inc. so do not fall under Anaconda’s licensing terms.

8.7 Overview Conda vs Pip

Many projects are now putting effort into creating wheels that allows for an easy installation of packages (e.g., `scipy`, `torch`, `kafka`, etc.) across many Linux distributions (see [PEP 600](https://peps.python.org/pep-600/)⁵⁹ and the [pypa/manylinux](https://github.com/pypa/manylinux)⁶⁰ project)

Pip is appropriate for:

- Pure Python projects
- Access to the comprehensive PyPI repository
- Projects with Python-only dependencies

Comparison: Conda vs pip:

⁵⁹ <https://peps.python.org/pep-0600/>

⁶⁰ <https://github.com/pypa/manylinux>

	pip	conda
Installs Packages	Wheels (binary) or source	Binaries/compiled
Used for	Python	Multiple languages
Dependency check	Yes	Yes

8.8 Virtual environments in Python

Virtual environments can be created via Python's `venv` module⁶¹, for convenience users may opt to store such environments in a centralized directory, conventionally named: `$HOME/.virtualenvs`, or in a directory within a user's project directory, conventionally named: `.venv` or `venv`, (see also: [Install packages in a virtual environment using pip and venv](#)⁶²):

```
$ python -m venv $HOME/.virtualenvs/<ENV_NAME>
$ source $HOME/.virtualenvs/<ENV_NAME>/bin/activate
# any successive installation via pip will occur in
# $HOME/.virtualenvs/<ENV_NAME> (no need to use `--user` flag):
$ pip install --upgrade pip
# a virtual environment can be deactivated with:
$ deactivate
```

A Python environment can be created using a `requirements.txt` file⁶³:

```
$ python -m venv $HOME/.virtualenvs/<ENV_NAME>
$ source $HOME/.virtualenvs/<ENV_NAME>/bin/activate
$ python -m pip install -r requirements.txt
```

A `requirements.txt` file can be created with:

```
$ pip freeze > requirements.txt
```

A limitation of the `venv` module is that a) it is only limited to Python packages, and b) it can only create virtual environments with a Python version as the one used to create the Python environment. Other tools exist to overcome the latter limitation, such as `conda`, `mamba`, `uv`, and `pyenv`.

Resources:

- [Understanding Conda and Pip](#)⁶⁴
- [Pip vs Conda: A Guide to Managing Python Packages for Data Scientists](#)⁶⁵
- [Pip vs Conda: key differences](#)⁶⁶

⁶¹ <https://docs.python.org/3/library/venv.html>

⁶² <https://packaging.python.org/en/latest/guides/installing-using-pip-and-virtual-environments/>

⁶³ https://pip.pypa.io/en/latest/user_guide/#requirements-files

⁶⁴ <https://www.anaconda.com/blog/understanding-conda-and-pip>

⁶⁵ <https://saturncloud.io/blog/pip-vs-conda-a-guide-to-managing-python-packages-for-data-scientists/>

⁶⁶ <https://saturncloud.io/blog/pip-vs-conda-a-guide-to-managing-python-packages-for-data-scientists/#pip-vs-conda-key-differences>

- Install packages in a virtual environment using pip and venv⁶⁷

8.9 Checking for Anaconda Repository Dependencies

Get a list of your environments:

```
$ conda env list
# conda environments:
#
myenv          /home/user/.conda/envs/myenv
test          /home/user/.conda/envs/test
base          * /apps/software/Miniforge3/24.1.2-0
```

For each environment’s path listed above, check where the installed packages came from:

```
$ conda list --explicit --prefix /home/user/.conda/envs/myenv | grep anaconda.com
https://repo.anaconda.com/pkgs/main/linux-64/libgd-2.2.5-h8e06009_4.conda
```

If you see any packages listed from “repo.anaconda.com”, these fall under the Anaconda Terms of Service and may require a license for continued use.

As of recent releases, Anaconda also ships a conda plugin (`conda-anaconda-tos`) that surfaces this coverage automatically: when conda accesses a Terms-of-Service-covered Anaconda channel (for example, the `main`, `r`, or `msys2` channels under `repo.anaconda.com`), the plugin prompts the user to accept, reject, or view the Terms of Service, and blocks the operation if rejected. Acceptance can also be managed non-interactively (for example via `conda tos accept`, the `plugins.auto_accept_tos` setting, or the `CONDA_PLUGINS_AUTO_ACCEPT_TOS` environment variable). The plugin is bundled by default in current Miniconda and Anaconda Distribution installers but is not present in community installers such as Miniforge, so the appearance of such a prompt is itself a clear signal that an environment depends on ToS-covered channels. See <https://github.com/anaconda/conda-anaconda-tos> for details.

8.10 uv

`uv` is an extremely fast Python package and project manager, written in Rust and developed by Astral. It has rapidly gained adoption across the Python community as a single tool that replaces `pip`, `pip-tools`, `pipx`, `twine`, `virtualenv`, and (for many workflows) `pyenv` and `Poetry`, offering substantially faster dependency resolution and installation. `uv` operates within the standard Python packaging ecosystem (PyPI and wheels) and can manage virtual environments, install packages, produce a universal cross-platform lockfile, and install and manage Python interpreter versions for unprivileged users. For projects whose dependencies are available as Python wheels, `uv` addresses the original motivation for reaching for Anaconda, namely materializing a specific Python and its dependencies on the local filesystem, without any reliance on Anaconda’s channels or Terms of Service.

`uv` does not, however, manage non-Python (binary) dependencies from conda channels the way conda-based tools do; it relies on PyPI wheels, which bundle their own compiled libraries. For workflows that genuinely require conda packages, a conda-compatible tool such as `Pixi` (described below) remains the better fit. Many researchers will find `uv` sufficient for pure-Python work and `Pixi` appropriate for the remainder; `Pixi` in fact uses `uv` internally to resolve and install PyPI dependencies, so the two can be complementary.

⁶⁷ <https://packaging.python.org/en/latest/guides/installing-using-pip-and-virtual-environments/>

Astral has also introduced `pyx`⁶⁸, a Python-native package registry (a commercial, early-access product) that provides an optimized, uv-aware mirror and proxy layer for PyPI and other public indexes. Of particular relevance to the secure-environment and compliance discussion, `pyx` can serve curated, pre-built wheels (including hardware-specific builds such as GPU/CUDA packages), enforce reproducible builds, and apply organizational compliance filters (for example by package age, popularity, or known vulnerabilities). Tooling of this kind points toward a path for institutions to obtain reliable, policy-compliant pre-built binaries without depending on Anaconda’s distribution channels. This remains an early-stage, commercial option rather than a free alternative, and its trajectory is uncertain following Astral’s [March 2026 announcement](#)⁶⁹ that it is joining OpenAI.

A guide to getting started with uv is available at the Astral documentation site here: <https://docs.astral.sh/uv/>

8.11 Pixi

Pixi is a fast and modern package manager that handles the same types of environments as Miniforge. It includes other features, but one of its main functions is to act as a package manager for conda environments. A new installation includes conda-forge as the default channel. Like Miniforge, it includes support for other conda channels, pip, etc.

A guide to migrating from Anaconda is available at the Pixi site here: https://pixi.prefix.dev/latest/switching_from/conda/

8.12 R and Anaconda

Anaconda can be useful to manage separate virtual environments and R versions. This functionality can be retained while avoiding paid channels by sticking to strict channel sources using `bioconda` and `conda-forge`. Pixi or miniforge are good options for this. Like with Python, some R packages may not be available in `conda-forge` but should be available in `CRAN`⁷⁰ or other non-conda repositories. Additionally, virtual environments are available within R itself via `renv`⁷¹. R also offers the ability to specify custom package library paths using `R_LIBS_USER / .libPaths()`, giving users control over which package directories R uses.

8.13 Block Anaconda Repo

As a sanity check, ATWG conducted a few tests, on nodes belonging to different HPC clusters, to install Python and R packages using open-source channels after blocking `Anaconda repo`. These tests were conducted on nodes running IPv6-only or IPv4-only environments with NAT/DNS64 support. Host firewall was enabled using `nftables` and IPv6 addresses or `iptables` and IPv4 addresses for `repo.anaconda.com` as resolved by the respective campus’ DNS. Following the block, we conducted tests on installing packages such as, `tensorflow`, `samtools`, and `bcftools` using open-source channels, `conda-forge` and `bioconda`. For R, we conducted the test after loading the `reticulate` library and installing Python packages using `py_install`, `virtualenv_install`, and `conda_install` on an R shell.

⁶⁸ <https://astral.sh/pyx>

⁶⁹ <https://astral.sh/blog/openai>

⁷⁰ <https://cran.r-project.org/>

⁷¹ <https://rstudio.github.io/renv/>

8.14 Spack

A primary reason researchers reach for a tool like Anaconda is to materialize a specific Python and its dependencies (both Python and non-Python) on the local filesystem as an unprivileged user, which is what a virtual environment provides. Two more recent developments can alleviate the need for that approach altogether: build-from-source package management, described here, and containerization, described below.

Spack is an HPC-centric package manager created at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) under U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) sponsorship, which allows users to instantiate one or more instances of itself, each of which can compile the whole world all the way down the dependency tree. This satisfies the need for getting specific Python versions onto the system for unprivileged users and/or non-Python dependencies. In fact, Spack has the ability to materialize proper virtual environments out of package requirements. The major downside here is in the combinatorial complexity of all the possibilities to satisfy these dependencies and the time cost for compiling everything. The initial setup of these instances can be a big lift but once done users can benefit from a shared build-cache and mirroring of packages to accelerate installation of packages.

8.15 Containers

Entirely separate from the present discussion is the modern quest for reproducibility and reusability of research software driving the adoption of container technologies like Docker, Apptainer, Podman, etc. Again, with the goal being to allow unprivileged users to bring their own Python and install both Python and non-Python dependencies into a self-contained environment, container technologies satisfy this need simultaneously with their added benefits to reproducibility (single hashable file, registry, DOI, etc.), and reusability (relocating whole software environments to new users and computing systems). Tools like Anaconda stem in large part from the fact that researchers did not have admin rights to the computing systems they run on, and they wanted more than one distinct instance of the software stack. Containers give them this, entirely obviating the use-case for package managers like Anaconda.